

**PRAGMATIC CONTENT OF MEDIA TEXTS IN TEACHING
METHODS FOR INTERCULTURAL STUDENTS**

Tursunov Jahongir Xusanovich

PhD Tashkent Medical Academy

To'raeva Go'zal Shukhrat qizi

Uzbekistan National University

named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Abstract. The main aim of the article is to try to formulate the principles and criteria of picking up foreign media texts which can be used as training material at English classes in Universities in order to form the intercultural competence together with the communicative one. The principles and criteria are worked out on the basis of some really existing television media texts.

Keywords: media text, intercultural competence, principles of picking up, criteria of picking up, foreign languages.

Currently, teaching foreign languages in Uzbek and Europe is carried out within the framework of an intercultural approach, according to which "the main task of the language of experience in higher education is the positive development of the personality and its self-awareness as a result of acquiring a new linguistic and cultural mastery of a foreign language the formation of communicative competence which includes linguistic, sociolinguistic and pragmatic competences, but also the acquisition of intercultural knowledge and skills, namely, formation.

The use of media texts in foreign language lessons is not an innovation in methodological science. Until recently, foreign language lessons were mainly used in newspaper and magazine articles, but in recent years, along with press materials, teachers began to use radio and television programs, as well as texts taken from the Internet. In this article, we will consider the principles and criteria for selecting

television media texts, namely news reports, with the aim of using them as educational material in foreign language classes at a university. Before proceeding to the methodological principles of selecting television media texts for working in foreign language classes at language faculties, we consider it appropriate to consider the advantages of these samples of foreign language and speech, which allow more efficient formation of communicative and intercultural competencies.

Firstly, television news programs of the country of the language being studied reflect the real course of events in all spheres of life of native speakers, which is undoubtedly of interest to students studying this foreign language and the culture of the country of this foreign language. The presence of interest, as a rule, leads to increased motivation of students, which is an important factor in the learning process in general. In addition, the penetration into the social subtext of all events taking place in the country, the analysis of the behavior of native speakers in specific socially determined situations allows a better understanding of national characteristics.

Secondly, a television news text is deployed simultaneously on three interconnected levels: a video sequence, musical accompaniment, and the actual verbal text. In the methodology of teaching foreign languages, it is indisputable that the perception of oral speech by a native speaker is more effective if the audio material is accompanied by a video. In addition, the video, accompanied by a soundtrack, creates the illusion of being in a foreign language environment.

Thirdly, the structure of the text part of the news is heterogeneous. In addition to the moderator's speech, it may include correspondent messages, a direct dialogue between the moderator and the correspondent, and interviewees' speech. Moreover, the news text is carefully prepared by a whole team of educated native speakers and voiced by them. All this suggests that news texts are the best example for students both in terms of language at all levels (phonetics, grammar, vocabulary, text), and in terms of monological and dialogical speech.

Another important point is the saturation of news texts with words denoting the realities of the country of the language being studied, as well as culture-specific vocabulary. Knowing the realities helps students to better master historical information, as well as information about the culture of the country of the language being studied. Vocabulary conveying culturally significant information is important for understanding the ideology of native speakers, their cultural values and orientations, as well as attitudes towards other peoples and events taking place in other countries. It is also possible to better understand the ideological and political views of native speakers in relation to events in other countries by analyzing the selection of information for television news plots, the perspective of presenting this information and comments by presenters and reporters, despite the constant desire for a more objective presentation of the news text.

The last argument in favor of texts of news programs as educational material will be their stability at all levels: at the level of format, content, language [2]. The organized and stable structure of the news text greatly facilitates the perception, and, accordingly, the understanding of the content. Dividing the news text into thematic blocks allows the teacher to select a list of words and phrases on this topic and use them as lexical material. The presence of a large number of phrases with verbs, passive and other grammatical constructions, repeating from program to program, also makes it possible to distinguish them as potentially easy to remember units. Further work with this lexical and grammatical material will lead to the use of this modern vocabulary and the most common grammatical constructions in the speech of students.

It is important to note that the authentic material, which is any foreign media text, is the most complex educational material, both in terms of language and in terms of background knowledge. In order to adequately perceive such material, students must not only have a certain level of a foreign language (presumably B1 level on a European scale and above), but also country-specific information, including the

history of the country of the language being studied and culture, as well as background knowledge of the global character (political, economic and cultural situation in the world, relations between different countries). Accordingly, it is advisable to use this material in senior courses of language faculties.

The abundance of language material does not solve the problem of choosing a media text as an educational material.

For the effective use of the texts of the media in the classroom, the teacher needs to clearly understand what purpose this or that material will be used for. T.G. Dobrosklonskaya believes that "in terms of language, an authentic text should be combined with learning goals, in other words, the selected text should be educational, ... embodying the features of one type or another of media texts and reflecting the basic vocabulary, stable phrases and, characteristic syntactic constructions and turns ". The content of the selected media text, according to T.G. Dobrosklonskaya, "must be universal in nature. the text should be deprived of any pronounced time references that quickly turn into "yesterday's" material that has lost its relevance. " [1]

V.V. Safonova believes that audio and video texts need to be selected, taking into account the communicative value, informative value and didactic cultural conformity of the text. The communicative value of any text should be understood as the degree of usefulness as a model of communication in a modern foreign language. The informational value of the text determines how much the information in the text opens up for the learner new significant aspects of the life of native speakers in all areas of real communication. The didactic cultural conformity of the text determines its cultural content, namely, the correspondence to the particular contingent of students (their age, interests, general cultural level of development, type of educational institution). Also, didactic cultural conformity is responsible for the lack of distorted cultural information and false stereotypes and the presence of priority universal cultural concepts

[1].

The principle of reliability of the source of information involves the use of news broadcasts of the highest priority television channels of the country of the studied foreign language.

By the principle of external media text parameters we mean the volume of the text, the duration of the sound, the tempo and clarity of the speech of the presenter and reporter, as well as the quality of the video image in the case of television media texts.

The principle of the internal parameters of the media text implies the language design of the text. In accordance with this principle, the teacher needs to correctly assess the complexity of lexical units and grams

textual constructions, the usefulness of lexical and grammatical material, the ability to improve the level of knowledge of a foreign language in the study of this material, the presence of language material that reflects the cultural characteristics and national character of native speakers.

The principle of thematic correspondence implies the choice of a mediatext (reportage) corresponding to the topic of the course for the given training period, as well as the presence in the text of topics and questions, the further discussion of which within the framework of the classes will allow to obtain intercultural knowledge and form intercultural skills and relationships.

The content of the above criteria may vary depending on the purpose of training and the level of knowledge of a foreign language.

An example of a mediatext selected in accordance with the presented principles and criteria is the following report on the topic [3] "Law. Crime and Punishment "(Law. Crime and Punishment) of the BBC1 television channel news release. In conclusion, it must be said that the ability to correctly select the video media text is insufficient for effective work with this material in the classroom. An important way of presenting the selected text, namely, the selection of lexical units to be studied, the system of exercises and tasks for working out lexical material, grammatical constructions, for

understanding the text both in terms of explicitly expressed information and context, a system of communicative exercises and exercises of a creative nature, homework variations. It is especially important within the framework of the currently prevailing intercultural approach to teaching foreign languages that all these tasks and exercises are intercultural in nature and contribute to the formation and improvement of not only communicative, but also intercultural competence.

References.

- 1.Общеввропейские компетенции владения иностранным языком: Изучение, обучение, оценка [Текст]. - М. : МГЛУ, 2005.
2. Добросклонская, Т.Г. Вопросы изучения медиатекстов (опять исследования современной английской медиаречи). Изд. 2-е, стереотипное [Текст] / Т.Г. Добросклонская. - М. : Едиториал УРСС, 2005.
- 3.Сафонова, В.В. Развитие культуры восприятия устной речи при обучении иностранному языку: современные методические проблемы и пути их решения [Текст] / В.В. Сафонова // Иностранные языки в школе. - 2011. - № 5. - С. 2-9.